

Conductometric Study of Mercuric- β -resorcylic Acid Complex

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In continuation of our work on complexes of β -resorcylic acid with $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ion¹, a study of conductance of mixtures of β -resorcylic acid and mercuric acetate has been undertaken, which confirms the complex formation between $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ ion and β -resorcylic acid in 1:1 ratio. The 1:1 complex between $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ ion and β -resorcylic acid had already been studied gravimetrically by Mukerji and Sant². $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ ion forms with aqueous β -resorcylic acid solution a white precipitate which settles down overnight, leaving a clear supernatant liquid.

$\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and β -resorcylic acid used were of B.D.H. 'AnalaR' and 'L.R.' quality respectively. A definite amount of acetic acid was added in the standard mercuric acetate solution to prevent hydrolysis. The experimental set-up and procedure were the same as in our previous communication³. The results are summarised in Table I where c represents the concentration of metal solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of β -resorcylic acid solution). The total volume in each case was kept at 12 ml.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	$c \times 10^{-3} M.$	$p.$	Fixed vol. of one component (ml).	Vol. at the peak or inflection (ml) metal.	Composition of the complex (Metal: β -resorcylic acid).
By Job's method (equimol. and nonequimol. soln.).					
1	4.000	1.000	..	6.0	1 : 1
2	3.333	1.000	..	6.0	1 : 1
3	2.500	1.000	..	6.0	1 : 1
4	4.000	0.500	..	4.0	1 : 1
5	3.333	0.500	..	4.0	1 : 1
6	3.333	0.333	..	3.0	1 : 1

1. Joshi and Jain, this *Journal*, communicated.

2. *Naturwiss.*, 1959, **46**, 24.

3. Joshi and Jain, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 241, 242; 1964, **41**, 33, 215, 711.

TABLE I (contd.)

Expt. No.	$c \times 10^{-3} M.$	$p.$	Fixed vol. of one component(ml).	Vol. at the peak or inflection(ml) metal.	Composition of the complex (Metal : β -resorcylic acid).
By monovariation method (direct and reverse titrations).					
7	4.000	1.000	4.0 each in direct and reverse titrations	4.0 each in direct and reverse titrations	1 : 1
8	3.333	1.000	Do	Do	1 : 1
9	2.500	1.000	Do	Do	1 : 1
10	4.000	0.500	2.0 metal in direct titration 6.0 reagent in reverse titration	4.0 reagent in direct titration 3.0 metal in reverse titration	1 : 1

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Conductometric Study of Mercurous-picrolonic Acid Complex

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In continuation of our work on complexes of picrolonic acid with various metals¹, a study of conductance of mixtures of picrolonic acid and mercurous nitrate has been undertaken which confirms the complex formation between Hg(I) ion and picrolonic acid in 1:1 ratio. Picrolonic acid has already been reported as a reagent for the microcrystalloscopic identification of univalent mercury². Hg(I) forms a yellow precipitate with picrolonic acid which completely settles down overnight, leaving a clear supernatant liquid. HgNO₃ · 2H₂O and picrolonic acid used were of B.D.H. 'AnalaR' and 'L.R.' quality, respectively. The experimental set-up and procedure were the same as in our previous communication¹. The results are summarised in Table I.

In the table, c represents the concentration of metal solution and p , the ratio c'/c (c' being the concentration of picrolonic acid solution). The total volume in each case was kept at 12 ml.

1. Joshi and Jain, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 241, 242; 1964, **41**, 711.

2. Alexandrova and Alexandrov, *Compt. Rend. Acad. Bulgare Sci.*, 1961, **14**, 595.

TABLE I

Exp. No.	$c \times 10^{-3} M.$	Fixed vol. of one component (ml).		Vol. at the peak or inflection (ml) metal.	Composition of the complex (Metal: picro-ionic acid).
By Job's method (equimol. and nonequimol. soln.)					
1	3.333	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
2	2.500	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
3	2.000	1.00	..	6.0	1 : 1
4	6.666	0.50	..	4.0	1 : 1
5	5.000	0.50	..	4.0	1 : 1
6	4.000	0.50	..	4.0	1 : 1
By monovariation method (direct and reverse titrations).					
7	3.333	1.00	4.0 each in direct and reverse titrations	4.0 each in direct and reverse titrations	1 : 1
8	2.500	1.00	Do	Do	1 : 1
9	6.666	0.50	3.0 metal in direct titration	6.0 reagent in direct titration	1 : 1
			6.0 reagent in reverse titration	3.0 metal in reverse titration	1 : 1

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